

Strong Nonlinear Optical Chirality Induced by Lattice Surface Modes on Plasmonic Metasurface

Shumei Chen^{†,§}, *Bernhard Reineke*[‡], *Guixin Li*^{||,*}, *Thomas Zentgraf*^{‡,*}, and *Shuang Zhang*^{§,*}

[†] School of Science, Harbin Institute of Technology, Shenzhen, 518055 China

[§] School of Physics & Astronomy, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, UK

[‡] Department of Physics, Paderborn University, Warburger Straße 100, D-33098 Paderborn,
Germany

^{||} Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Shenzhen Institute for Quantum Science and
Engineering, Southern University of Science and Technology, Shenzhen 518055 China

* E-mail: ligx@sustech.edu.cn; thomas.zentgraf@upb.de; s.zhang@bham.ac.uk;

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ABSTRACT

Optical metasurfaces, consisting of spatially variant meta-atoms, represent a new kind of optical platforms for controlling the wavefront of light, with which many interesting applications such as metalens, optical holography have been successfully demonstrated. Further extension of the optical functionalities of metasurfaces into nonlinear optical regime has led to unprecedented control over the local optical nonlinear generation processes. It has been shown that the nonlinear optical metasurface with achiral geometries could exhibit intrinsic optical chirality in second- and third-harmonic generations. In this work, we propose an alternative approach for achieving giant nonlinear optical chirality in achiral plasmonic metasurfaces by exploiting the lattice surface modes of plasmonic metasurfaces. Specifically, we theoretically and experimentally demonstrate the strong circular dichroism for second harmonic generation (SHG) on plasmonic metasurfaces consisting of split ring resonator meta-atoms. The giant nonlinear circular dichroism is attributed to the contribution from lattice surface modes at fundamental wavelengths. Our findings may open new routes to design novel nonlinear optical devices with strong optical chirality.

Optical chirality, manifested by optical activity and circular dichroism (CD), arises from phase and absorption differences between light with left- and right-circular polarizations (LCP and RCP) when propagating in a medium. It is well-known that the chiral optical response from natural materials is usually very weak. However, it can be greatly enhanced with the strong resonances in chiral metamaterials,⁽¹⁾⁻⁽⁹⁾ which leads to a broad range of applications such as negative refraction,⁽¹⁾ compact circular polarizers,⁽²⁾ enhancement of molecules' chirality⁽³⁾⁻⁽⁵⁾ and so on. On the other hand, the advent of metasurfaces revolutionizes the design of ultrathin optical devices by using spatially variant meta-atoms. Several optical devices with planar designs such as metalenses, metasurface holograms, and polarization beam splitter have been demonstrated.⁽¹⁰⁾⁻⁽¹⁴⁾ It is usually expected that metasurfaces, unlike the three-dimensional (3D) metamaterials, cannot introduce strong optical chirality due to the limited propagation length of light. However, in the nonlinear optical regime, the giant nonlinear CD has been realized from achiral plasmonic metasurfaces with three- and four-fold rotational symmetry.⁽¹⁵⁾ In the reported results, the values of CD of nonlinear harmonic generations are close to the theoretical limits despite the linear optical chirality is almost negligible under normal incidence of a fundamental wave (FW). These reported results show that two-dimensional metasurfaces with planar chirality are suitable candidates for realizing giant optical chirality in nonlinear optical processes such as harmonic generations,⁽¹⁶⁾⁻⁽²⁰⁾ four-wave mixing,⁽²¹⁾ two-photon emission⁽²²⁾ and so on.

Under normal incidence of light, the main focus has been on the intrinsic optical chirality of artificial materials. In comparison, the giant optical chirality can also be acquired from the extrinsic chirality induced by the oblique incidence of light.⁽²³⁾⁻⁽²⁶⁾ This technique was widely used to probe the chirality of molecule thin films and plasmonic metasurfaces through second harmonic generation (SHG).^{(16), (17), (24)-(26)} However, large incident angles (tens of degrees) were usually

required to generate large extrinsic optical chirality, and thus putting a limit to the miniaturization of the optical systems. Recently, it was shown that linear optical chirality could be greatly enhanced by optimizing the mode coupling effects, such as the lattice plasmon mode supported by a plasmonic metasurface consisting of split ring resonators (SRRs).²⁷ Interestingly, the SRR meta-atom also exhibits strong nonlinear optical response in SHG process,^{(1), 28-35} partially due to the fact that the gold SRR meta-atom is capable of inducing strong magnetic resonance when interacting with the FW ^{(1), 28-35} It is expected that the SHG efficiency from the SRR metasurface can be further improved by considering the surface lattice resonances²⁷ either at the fundamental or second harmonic wavelengths³³.

In this work, we realize a strong SHG-CD effect by utilizing lattice surface modes (LSM) on the plasmonic metasurface consisting of split ring resonator (SRR) meta-atoms. The SRR metasurface does not have planar chirality and exhibits negligible optical chirality as in three-dimensional metamaterials. Here, we demonstrate a new strategy of realizing strong nonlinear CD by exploiting both LSMs on the SRR metasurface and extrinsic optical chirality introduced by the oblique incidence of the FW. The spin sensitive LSMs arise from the strong coupling between localized plasmon resonance and the Rayleigh anomaly (RA) mode. It is shown that the maximum nonlinear CD at SHG frequencies is around three times higher than for the FW in the linear optical regime. Thus, it is expected that the spin sensitive LSMs hold great potentials for designing novel nonlinear chiral- optical devices for bio-sensing or information processing.

Figure 1a and Figure 1b show the schematic diagrams for the nonlinear optical chirality that arises from the SRR metasurface under both RCP and LCP fundamental waves with ± 10 degree oblique incident angle. Figure 1c illustrates the experimental setup for the SHG-CD measurement. For normal incident, the metasurface plane is kept parallel to the x-y plane as shown in Figure 1c.

When the incident angle is tilted to ± 10 degree, the metasurface plane is rotated ± 10 degree along the y-axis which is parallel to the vertical arm of the SRR meta-atom. After passing through the metasurface, the transmitted white light or SHG waves are collected by an objective lens and finally measured by using an EMCDD equipped spectrometer. Figure 1d shows the geometrical parameters of the SRR meta-atom and the scanning electron microscopy image of the SRR metasurface used in this work. The plasmonic metasurface consists of 30 nm thick gold SRRs that are fabricated on a glass substrate and then coated by a 150 nm thick MgF_2 film. For the U-shaped SRR meta-atom, the length of the horizontal and the vertical nanorods are 220 nm and 120 nm, respectively. These SRR meta-atoms are arranged in a square lattice with a period of 540 nm in both x- and y- directions. The strong localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) from a single SRR meta-atom originates from the oscillations of surface charges induced by incident light. In the linear optical regime, there are three main resonant modes supported by an individual SRR meta-atom excited by either TM (p-) or TE (s-) linearly polarized incident waves.³⁶ As shown in Figure 2a and Figure 2b, for TM polarization, the direction of the incident electric field is parallel to the x-axis and the long arm of the bottom nanorod, thus the dipole and quadrupole modes can be excited at longer (~ 1200 nm) and shorter wavelengths (~ 850 nm), respectively. In comparison, for TE polarization, the direction of the polarization is perpendicular to the incident plane (x-z plane), which gives the incident electric field paralleling to the long arm of the vertical nanorod. In this case, only the dipole mode can be excited, and it can be very close to the quadrupole mode if the arm length of the vertical nanorod is judiciously chosen.

By deliberately assembling these SRR meta-atoms into a square lattice with period of P, the plasmonic resonant modes arising from each meta-atom can be coupled with the collective mode induced by the Rayleigh anomaly, leading to either constructive or destructive interferences

between the optical modes near the localized plasmon resonant wavelengths of the meta-atoms. This lattice surface resonance mode, or Rayleigh anomaly mode, can be excited when the following condition is met.

$$\lambda_{RA}^{\pm}(\theta) = nP(1 \pm \sin(\theta)) \quad (1)$$

Where λ_{RA} is the wavelength of the RA resonance mode, P is the lattice constant of the metasurface, θ is the incident angle of light, n is the refractive index of the surrounding medium, the '+' and '-' sign corresponds to the positive and negative diffraction order of the RA resonance mode, respectively. In this work, the RA resonance occurs at a wavelength of 724 nm under normal incident and is shifted to 850 nm with an incident angle of +10 degree. In parts c-d of Figure 2, we plot the near-field distributions of the real part of E_y to characterize the two LSPR modes of the SRR meta-atoms under excitation of TM and TE waves. It is found that both the quadrupole mode and the vertical dipole mode are located around the wavelength of 850 nm, indicating that under certain oblique incident angle the combined dipole-quadrupole modes can be coupled with the lattice resonance, and finally leading to a strong optical chiral optical response on the plasmonic metasurface.

As shown in Figure 3, we further characterize the linear optical properties of the SRR metasurface by using circularly polarized (CP) FW under both normal incidence and ± 10 degree oblique incidence. For the incident angle $\theta = \pm 10$ degree, the metasurface is rotated in the incident plane by either clockwise or counter-clockwise direction. The unit vector of left-hand circularly polarized (LCP) light e_L and right-hand circularly polarized (RCP) light e_R is defined by $e_L = e_p + ie_s$ and $e_R = e_p - ie_s$, respectively. Here e_p and e_s are the unit vectors of TM (p-) and TE

(s-) polarized waves, respectively. The circular dichroism of transmitted light is defined as: $CD = (T_{RCP} - T_{LCP}) / (T_{RCP} + T_{LCP})$, with T_{RCP} and T_{LCP} being the transmittance of the SRR metasurface under RCP and LCP illumination, respectively. Under normal incidence, the achiral property of the SRR metasurface is confirmed by both the simulated and experimental measured transmission spectra shown in Figure 3a and Figure 3b. We find that the transmittance of both LCP and RCP waves are almost the same, leading to the negligible CD values in the experiments. Moreover, according to Equation 1, the RA resonance will split into two modes at a wavelength of 850 nm and 650 nm, respectively. In comparison, for light from oblique incidence, a strong extrinsic chirality, which is caused by interplay between the RA mode and LSP mode, will be introduced to the system. As shown in Figure 3c and Figure 3d, for an LCP wave which is incident at an angle of +10 degree, the resonant wavelength of the hybrid RA-LSPR-polariton mode is red shifted from 850 nm to 900 nm due to the constructive interference between the lattice surface mode and the LSPR mode.³⁷ While in the case of RCP waves, the resonant wavelength is blue shifted to 800 nm because of the destructive interference of the two modes. Hence, the difference of transmittance of the LCP/RCP results in a linear optical CD effect with a maximum calculated value of 0.3 as shown in Figure 3e. The CD value in this work is lower than that in Reference 27, mainly due to the much thinner thickness of gold we used to ease the nanofabrication. While the incident angle is tuned to -10 degree, the chiral optical of LCP/RCP waves is flipped, which gives a CD value of -0.3 in this case. The measured CD with only ± 0.1 maximum values shown in Figure 3f is even smaller than the theoretical value due to the possible defects of the sample. The observed optical phenomena in the linear optical regime are in accordance with previously reported work by De Leon et al.²⁷

It is well known that for chiral materials, the second harmonic generation circular dichroism (SHG-CD) is significant more sensitive than linear CD effects.^{15-17, 23-26} Therefore, in the following, we study case if the chirality can be enhanced in second harmonic generation process with the spin sensitive LSR mode on the metasurface. The SHG signal generated from the SRR metasurface is measured by using a spectrally tuneable femtosecond-OPO laser (repetition frequency: 82 MHz, pulse duration: ~ 200 fs) as source of the fundamental waves. After passing through a linear polarizer and a quarter-wave plate, the circularly polarized FW is slightly focused by a lens (N. A. = 0.05) and then incident onto the metasurface with a spot size of ~ 50 μm in diameter. The SHG signal from the SRR meta-atoms is then collected by an infinity-corrected objective lens (magnification = 10x, N.A. = 0.3) and the FW is filter by band-pass filters. Finally, an Andor spectrometer (SP300i) with EMCCD detector is used to record the SHG spectrum. In Figure 4a, we first plot the wavelength dependent SHG intensity by scanning the wavelength of the circularly polarized FW from 800 nm to 900 nm under normal incidence. It is clearly observed that for both LCP (blue dot line) and RCP (black dot line) excitation, the peak response of SHG occurs at 850 nm, which corresponds to the dipole-quadrupole plasmon resonance wavelength shown in Figure 3a. Theoretically, it is expected that the CD of SHG waves is zero since no linear and nonlinear chirality can be introduced under normal incidence of the FW. This is reflected by the experimental results. The small discrepancy from theoretical prediction may be attributed to the imperfections of the sample and the experimental setup. As shown in Figure 4b, when the incident angle of the FW changes to +10 degree, the intensity of the SHG under excitation of RCP FW approaches its maximum value at the wavelength of 820 nm, which is almost 3 times higher than that in the case of LCP-FW excitation. On the other hand, when the incident angle of the FW is -10 degree, the SHG intensity under excitation of LCP FW approaches its maximum value at

the same wavelength as shown in Figure 4c. By defining the CD value for the SHG waves as SHG-CD = $(I_{RCP} - I_{LCP})/(I_{RCP} + I_{LCP})$, we can obtain the CD spectrum shown in Figure 4d. In the experiment, the measured maximum value of the SHG-CD is up to 0.6, which is six times higher than the maximum measured CD value (Figure 3f) in the linear optical measurement.

To better understand the measured nonlinear CD results from the gold SRR metasurface device under normal and oblique incidence of the FW, numerical simulations for the SHG process are conducted. The nonlinear polarization distribution that contributes to the SHG is calculated based on the linear optical responses at the fundamental and second harmonic wavelengths.^{38, 39} Specifically, the nonlinear optical response of the metasurface at the SHG wavelength is described by a spatially varying surface polarization $P^{2\omega}(r) = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E(r) \cdot E(r)$, which depends on the complex field $E(r)$ and the nonlinear susceptibility $\chi^{(2)}$ of the material at the location r , respectively. Finally, the contribution to the far-field signal from the nonlinear polarization of the SHG at each local point can be calculated by the following equation:

$$E_{SHG}(r') = \int G(r', r) \cdot P_{SHG}(r) d^3r \quad (2)$$

As shown in Figure 4, the spectral response of the SHG from the SRR metasurface is calculated for the FW incident for zero (Figure 4a) and ± 10 degrees (Figure 4b and 4c). It is found that under both normal and oblique incidence, the nonlinear optical calculations agree with the experimental results. However, the calculated maximum values of the nonlinear CD is higher than that of the measured ones due to the imperfection of the nanofabrication. In principle, the performance of the nonlinear chirality could be further improved by optimizing the geometrical parameters and quality of metasurface device.

In conclusion, we designed an SRR metasurface which exhibits strong linear optical chirality mediated by the lattice surface resonance and oblique incidence of light. We showed that the optical chirality in linear optical regime is greatly enhanced in the SHG process by deliberately aligning the frequency of fundamental wave with the lattice resonance mode under a small oblique incident angle. The proposed nonlinear metasurface devices⁴⁰⁻⁴² pave new routes for designing novel chiral-optical functionalities in nonlinear optical regimes.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Schematic of the nonlinear measurement of circular dichroism from SRR metasurface. (a) and (b) Schematic of the circular dichroism for illumination with ± 10 degree oblique incident LCP and RCP fundamental waves on the SRR metasurface. (c) The measurement setup of circular dichroism for SHG waves: a broadband femtosecond laser output at near-infrared wavelengths with circular polarizations are either normal or obliquely incident onto the gold SRR metasurface. The SRR metasurface is rotated -10 degree and $+10$ degree to $-z$ and $+z$ direction along y -axis for obliquely incident measurements, respectively. The incident plane is the x - z plane. The SHG waves are collected by the objective lens and finally detected by using spectrometer in the transmission direction. FW: fundamental wave; LP: linear polarizer; QWP: quarter-wave plate; L1 and L2: lenses; OB1: objective lens; F1: filter; (d) Geometric parameters of the SRR meta-atom and SEM images of gold metasurface fabricated on ITO coated glass substrate. The scale bar is 500 nm.

Figure 2. Field distribution of localized plasmonic mode on the gold SRR metasurface. (a) and (b) Schematic of quadrupole and dipole modes under excitation of TM and TE waves from normal incidence. For TM polarization, the electric field is parallel to the x-axis. For TE polarized wave, the electric field is perpendicular to the incident plane (x-z plane). (c) and (d) Calculated field distribution of light in a unit cell of the SRR metasurface. For linear (H-) polarized incident light at a wavelength of 850 nm, the absolute values of electric field $|E_y|$ are plotted in X-Y ($z=0$) plane of a unit cell. Arbitrary unit was used in the colour maps in (c) and (d).

Figure 3. Linear optical property of the gold SRR metasurface. (a) Calculated and (b) measured linear transmission spectra of the SRR metasurface for light with RCP states for incident angles of zero and ± 10 degrees. (c) Calculated and (d) measured linear transmission spectra of the SRR metasurface for light with LCP states for incident angles of zero and ± 10 degrees. (e) and (f) are the calculated and measured CD spectra obtained from the calculation and measurement in (a)-(d).

Figure 4. Polarization dependent SHG spectra of the SRR metasurface. Measured and calculated SHG spectra under FW with LCP and RCP states, which are incident from zero (a), and ± 10 degrees (b)-(c). (d) Measured (Exp) and calculated (Cal) wavelength dependent SHG-CD. The values for the squares in (a) are obtained from the calculation (Cal) of SHG-CD based on the experimentally determined values of the effective nonlinear susceptibilities. The maximum SHG-CD is obtained when the fundamental wavelength is around 850 nm. The deviation between the calculated and experimental data is mainly due to the imperfections of nanofabrication.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The supporting information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: ligx@sustech.edu.cn;

*E-mail: thomas.zentgraf@upb.de;

*E-mail: s.zhang@bham.ac.uk.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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